

Quantitative Analysis of Consolidation of Thermoplastic Composite Preforms

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SUMMARY: Due to the high viscosity of thermoplastic matrices it is difficult to rapidly wet out and consolidate thermoplastic composite preforms containing dry fibers. Consequently, consolidation is often the rate limiting step in processing thermoplastic composites. In order to develop comprehensive quantitative models of consolidation a series of fibers, resins and fiber preforms have been studied. The fibers investigated include glass, carbon and sisal. The resins studied include polypropylene, nylon 6 and polyphenylene sulfide (PPS). The fiber preforms investigated were random mats and unidirectional powder-coated tows. For the mat preforms, a transverse Kozeny constant of 7.9 was calculated from transient permeation experiments using a non-Newtonian permeation model. For the towpreg preforms, a transverse Kozeny constant of 362 was calculated. The Kozeny values for each preform were independent of the fibers, resins, and processing conditions studied. The non-Newtonian permeation model predicted the permeation well. The average percent error between the experimental data and the permeation model was less than 6%. Two mechanistic models predicted the transient permeation well.

KEYWORDS: Consolidation, Permeation, Thermoplastic, Modeling

INTRODUCTION

Continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics are commercially attractive materials. Low cost and low density thermoplastics, like polypropylene, can be used as matrices. Thermoplastic composites often possess excellent damage tolerance and damping characteristics, which are sought for transportation and recreation products. Thermoplastic composites are relatively easy to recycle and well suited for rapid manufacturing.

A critical issue in the manufacture of thermoplastic composites is combining the thermoplastics with the reinforcing fibers. Due to the high viscosity of most thermoplastics a significant amount of time must be provided for the thermoplastic to fully permeate a fiber mat or bundle. Since the consolidated thermoplastic composite is stiff, often full consolidation is deferred until the final product is molded. The unconsolidated preform is more flexible and therefore more conformable. Since curing reactions are not an issue in processing thermoplastic composites the rate limiting step is often the time required to completely wet all the dry fibers

Darcy's law, shown in equation 1, has been used extensively to model the flow of fluids through porous media. Darcy's law relates the average fluid velocity, u , to the permeability of the porous media, S , the fluid viscosity, μ , the pressure difference, ΔP , and the bed thickness, X . It should be noted that u is a vector and S is a tensor when studying flow through fiber media. In this research, transverse flow, or flow perpendicular to the fiber axis, was studied.

$$u = \frac{S \Delta P}{\mu X} \quad (1)$$

Many researchers have used the Kozeny-Carman relation, shown in equation 2, to describe the permeability of fiber beds. The Kozeny-Carman equation relates the permeability to the fiber radius, r_f , the fiber volume fraction of the fiber media, v_f , and the Kozeny constant, k . The

Kozeny constant, shown in equation 3, is the product of a shape factor that depends on the shape of the capillary cross section, K_o , and the square of the tortuosity of the flow path through fibers, K_1 . Astrom *et al* [1] gives a detailed description of the derivation of equations 1-3.

$$S = \frac{r_f^2 (1 - v_f)}{K_o K_1^2 v_f^2} \quad (2)$$

$$k = K_o K_1^2 \quad (3)$$

The objective of this work is to study the permeation step of the consolidation process for thermoplastic composites. The goal is to obtain a simple, universally valid predictive model. The model needs to be valid for different processing conditions and different materials. Therefore, experiments were conducted using different fibers, matrices, and processing conditions. In addition, two types of composite preforms were studied: random mat preforms and powder-coated towpreg.

THEORY

Since the thermoplastics studied were non-Newtonian a power law version of equation 2 was used. With this modification the rate of permeation of the advancing flow front, V , is:

$$V = \left(\frac{4n}{1+3n} \right) \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{\frac{1+n}{n}} \left(\frac{\varepsilon^{2n+1}}{(1-\varepsilon)^{1+n}} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \left(\frac{1}{K_o (K_1)^{\frac{1+n}{n}}} \right) \left(r_f^{\frac{1+n}{n}} \right) \left(\frac{\Delta P}{mX} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (4)$$

where n = the power-law flow index, m = the power-law consistency index and ε = the porosity of fiber bed. Equation 4 can be integrated for constant temperature and pressure to obtain the permeation depth, X , as a function of time, t :

$$X = \left[\left(\frac{1+n}{1+3n} \right) \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \left(\frac{\varepsilon^{2n+1}}{(1-\varepsilon)^{1+n}} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \left(\frac{1}{K_o (K_1)^{\frac{1+n}{n}}} \right) \left(r_f^{\frac{1+n}{n}} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{m} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} t \right) \right]^{\frac{n}{1+n}} \quad (5)$$

This permeation depth is illustrated in Figure 1. X_c represents the completion of permeation when all the fibers have been contacted by the matrix and no voids remain.

Figure 1: Schematic of resin permeation depth in a fiber bed.

In equation 5, K_0 , which depends on the capillary cross section, is assigned a value of 2 for the random mats and a value of 3 for the aligned powder-coated tows. A value of 2 is appropriate for a cylindrical pore whereas 3 is used for rectangular pores. The tortuosity, K_1 , is usually determined experimentally. Since K_1 is obtained experimentally the arbitrary assignments for K_0 are compensated by the empirical determination of K_1 . Hence, equation 5 is considered a semi-empirical model. Alternatively, models describing two dimensional, creeping flow of a power-law fluid transverse to the fiber axis can be compared with this semi-empirical model. Two models are considered here.

The model due to Vijaysri *et al* (2) focuses on flow past a single cylinder, as illustrated in Figure 2. The dotted circle refers to a hypothetical envelope of fluid. This model is best suited for fiber beds with high porosity. Thus, this model will only be considered for the experiments with random mats.

Figure 2. Schematic of geometry assumption for Vijaysri model.

The permeation depth based on the Vijaysri model is:

$$X = \left[\left[2 \left(\frac{1+n}{n} \right) \left(\frac{\pi}{(1-\varepsilon)\Lambda} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right] \left[r_f^{\frac{n+1}{n}} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{m} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} t \right] \right]^{\frac{n}{n+1}} \quad (6)$$

where Λ is a loss coefficient, which is a complex function of porosity and power-law flow index (2, 3). A permeation experiment is not necessary to evaluate equation 6.

A second analytical model, due to Brusckhe and Advani (4), is for transverse flow through a square array of cylinders. This model is best suited for the low porosity conditions encountered in the unidirectionally aligned powder-coated tows. This model is applied to the random mats even though such mats do not approximate a square array. The permeation depth based on this model is presented in equation 8. In this expression l = the fiber radius/ the half distance between fibers, which is only a function of the porosity. The angle, α , in equation 8 is

$$\alpha = \arctan \sqrt{\frac{1-l}{1+l}} \quad (7)$$

$$X = \left[\left(\frac{1+n}{n} \right) \left(\frac{1}{2^n} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \frac{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left(\frac{2n}{1+2n} \right)^n \left[(1+l)^{-(2n+1)} (\cos^2 \alpha)^{2n+1} \alpha^{-4n-1} \frac{\Gamma\left(2n+\frac{1}{2}\right)}{\Gamma(2n+1)} \right]^{-1} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}}}{l^{n+1}} \left(r_f^{\frac{1+n}{n}} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{m} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} t \right) \right]^{\frac{n}{n+1}} \quad (8)$$

Γ = the gamma function. A permeation experiment is not necessary to evaluate equation 8.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials Composite processing models need to be valid for different resin and fiber combinations. Because of this, different resin and fiber combinations were used for both the mats and powder-coated tows. Glass, carbon, and sisal mats were used for the mat preforms. The glass mat was type 8447 from Johns Manville. Technical Fibre supplied the carbon mat and Georgia Composites supplied the sisal mat. The mats were composed of single fiber filaments. Figure 3 is a SEM photograph of the carbon mat. The thickness of the fiber mats, while under pressure, was determined and used to calculate the fiber volume fraction in the mat. The thickness measurements, fiber volume fractions, and other properties of the mat are listed in Table 1.

E-glass and carbon fibers were used as the reinforcements in the powder-coated tows. Figure 4 is a SEM photograph of a powder-coated carbon fiber tow ("towpreg"). Fiber properties for the towpreg are located in Table 2. For each resin and fiber combination for the towpreg, two different weight percents were used, and these values are located in Table 2. Applied Fiber Systems' TFE6N6 and TFC6N6 were used for powder-coated tow.

Polypropylene and nylon 6 sheets were used as the matrix in the fiber mat preforms. The polypropylene sheet was Resinol Type O[®] from Allied Resinous Products, and the nylon sheet was Nylatron[®] 907 from DSM. A different grade of nylon 6 was used as the matrix in the towpreg. The rheology of the matrices was studied using a parallel plate rheometer. The power law parameters, m and n, were determined from viscosity versus shear rate curves, and the parameter values are listed in Table 1 for the fiber mat matrices and in Table 2 for the matrices in the powder-coated towpregs.

Composite Production Compression molding was used to make the composites in this study. Figure 5 is a schematic of the experimental set-up. For the mat preforms, sheets of resin and fiber were stacked as shown in Figure 6 in a 25 cm by 25 cm aluminum mold. The sides of the mold were closed to prevent flow along the fiber direction. The mold was placed in a hot press and allowed to reach processing temperature. At this point, the processing pressure was applied and the transient thickness change of the sample was measured using a linear variable displacement transducer (LVDT).

Figure 3: SEM photograph of carbon fiber mat. The bar is 50 μm .

Figure 4: SEM photographs of carbon/nylon 6 towpreg. The bar on the photograph on the left is 7 μm , and the bar length is 150 μm on the right photograph.

Table 1: Properties of Fibers and Resins for Mat Preforms

	Radius	Area weight	Fiber		Thickness	Fiber volume fraction
			Fiber density	Pressure		
	[μm]	[g/cm^2]	[g/cm^3]	[MPa]	[cm]	
glass	8	0.0229	2.54	1.38	0.031	0.29
glass	8	0.0229	2.54	2.76	0.028	0.32
carbon	4	0.0245	1.7	1.38	0.049	0.29
carbon	4	0.0245	1.7	2.76	0.046	0.31
sisal	125	0.0279	1.45	0.34	0.045	0.42

	Resin		Temperature
	m	n	
	[Pas^m]		[$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
polypropylene	13,400	0.65	170
polypropylene	10,300	0.65	190
nylon 6	14,400	0.71	230

Compression molding was also used to make composites from the powder-coated tows. The towpreg was wound onto a 25 cm by 25 cm mandrel using a filament winder. The ends of the resulting 25 cm by 25 cm towpreg sheets were spot welded with a hot iron. Twelve sheets of the preform were stacked and placed in the aluminum mold, and the same procedure as described above was followed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Table 1, the calculated fiber volume fractions of the compressed mats were between 0.29 and 0.42. A fiber volume fraction value of 0.76 was calculated for the towpreg, and this value was constant for the different applied pressures, different global weight percents, and different fibers.

Table 2: Properties of fibers and resin for towpreg

	Radius [μm]	Density [g/cm^3]	Fiber
			Fiber volume fraction
carbon	3.5	1.78	0.76
glass	8	2.58	0.76

	m [Pas^n]	n	Resin
			Temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
nylon 6	304	0.93	230
nylon 6	186	0.93	260
PPS	63	0.96	310

Figure 5: Schematic of experimental apparatus

Figure 6: Mat preform experimental set-up.

The estimated shear rates were between 0.4 and 1.5 s^{-1} for the matrices used in the mat preforms and between 1.4 and 5.8 s^{-1} for the matrices used in the towpreg. Therefore, the rheology experiments were run in these shear rate ranges. As expected, the resins exhibited shear-thinning behavior. The calculated power law parameters are listed in Table 1 for the mat preform matrices and in Table 2 for the towpreg matrices.

The experimental, transient permeation depth, $X(t)$, was calculated using equation 9. Referring to Figures 1 and 5, equation 9 is a mass balance where Δh is the thickness change of the sample. The same mass balance method is used to calculate the permeation depth for the towpreg.

$$X(t) = \frac{\Delta h(t)}{2\varepsilon} \quad (9)$$

The thickness change data was fitted to equation 5 to determine K_1 , and equation 3 was used to determine the Kozeny constant at each specific condition listed in Tables 3 and 4. An average value for the Kozeny constant was calculated from the specific condition Kozeny constants.

The experimental penetration depth, X_{exp} , was compared with the theoretical penetration depth, X_{pred} , using equation 10 where E is the percent error and p is the number of experimental observations. The percent error was calculated using the Kozeny constant fitted for the specific processing conditions. A second percent error was also calculated by using the average value of the Kozeny constants in the permeation model. Percent errors were calculated for the two other flow models where they were applied.

$$E = 100 \frac{\sum_{i=1}^p \frac{|X_{\text{exp}_i} - X_{\text{pred}_i}|}{X_{\text{exp}_i}}}{p} \quad (10)$$

Table 3: Kozeny constant results for mat preform processing

Fiber mat	Resin	Pressure [MPa]	Temperature [°C]	Kozeny constant, k
glass	PP	1.38	170	7.8
glass	PP	1.38	190	7.7
glass	PP	2.76	170	8.3
glass	PP	2.76	190	7.8
glass	N6	1.38	230	8.3
glass	N6	2.76	230	8.2
carbon	PP	1.38	170	7.8
carbon	PP	1.38	190	7.5
carbon	PP	2.76	170	7.5
carbon	PP	2.76	190	7.8
carbon	N6	1.38	230	7.8
carbon	N6	2.76	230	7.8
sisal	PP	0.34	170	8
sisal	PP	0.34	190	7.8
			Average	7.9
			Standard Dev.	0.3

As shown in Table 3, Kozeny constant values between 7.5 and 8.3 were calculated for the mat preform processing. An average Kozeny constant of 7.9 was determined from the fourteen different operating conditions. The average Kozeny constant value compares well with some values reported in the literature [1] for flow through random fiber beds. An analysis of variance showed that the Kozeny constant does not vary with pressure, fiber type, fluid type, or viscosity. For the 12 conditions in Table 3 the errors between the experimental penetration depth, X_{exp} , and the predicted penetration depth, X_{pred} , ranged from 1 and 9 %. The average error was 4 %. Because the range in calculated Kozeny constants was so small, the percent error when using the average value of 7.9 did not affect the accuracy of the permeation model. Figures 7 and 8 show that the permeation model predicts the penetration depth well.

Also shown in Figures 7 and 8 are the predictions based Vijaysri's model based on flow around a single fiber and Brusckke's model for flow through a square array. The Brusckke model virtually matches the semi-empirical model based on the specific Kozeny constant for these experiments. The average error for the semi-empirical model is 4.0 % whereas the average error for the Brusckke model is 4.3 %. The average error for Vijaysri's model is 6.3 % which is also very good. The excellent predictions from Brusckke's model are surprising since the random mats are far removed from the assumed square array for the model. Since both models work so well the dominating geometric features must be the mat porosity and cylindrical shape of the fibers.

Table 4: Experimentally determined Kozeny constants for towpreg

Towpreg	Resin Weight Percent, [%]	Pressure [MPa]	Temperature [°C]	Kozeny constant
carbon/N6	43	0.52	230	358
carbon/N6	43	0.52	260	353
carbon/N6	43	1.03	230	353
carbon/N6	43	1.03	260	353
carbon/N6	33	0.52	230	381
carbon/N6	33	0.52	260	362
carbon/N6	33	1.03	230	355
carbon/N6	33	1.03	260	352
glass/N6	34	0.52	230	347
glass/N6	34	0.52	260	411*
glass/N6	34	150	230	387*
glass/N6	34	150	260	689*
glass/N6	26	0.52	230	357
glass/N6	26	0.52	260	351
glass/N6	26	150	230	372
glass/N6	26	150	260	423*
carbon/PPS	48	0.52	310	361
carbon/PPS	48	150	310	380
carbon/PPS	38	0.52	310	366
carbon/PPS	38	150	310	387
			Average	362
			Standard Dev.	12.2

*Note: Data not included in average

Figure 7: Penetration depth versus time for glass mat/PP. The processing pressure is 2.76 MPa and the processing temperature is 190 °C. The standard deviation of the penetration depth is ~0.004 mm. The error bars are too small to be visible on the graph.

For the towpregs the Kozeny constant values shown in Table 4 range from 347 to 387, excluding the four conditions marked with an *. For these four excluded conditions virtually complete

Figure 8: Penetration depth versus time for carbon mat/N6. The processing pressure is 1.38 MPa and the processing temperature is 230 °C. The standard deviation of the penetration depth is ~0.01mm.

permeation occurred within the experimental time period. Therefore artificially high Kozeny constants were obtained from fitting the transient penetration depth responses.

The average Kozeny constant for the towpregs of 362 is much higher than the mats due to the low porosity of the towpregs. As illustrated in Figure 9, the prediction achieved using a Kozeny constant of 353, the best value for this experiment, in the semi-empirical model is very good. The Brusckke model is just as good and does not require any fitting. The Vijaysri model is not suited for these low porosity towpregs and has not been applied to these towpreg experiments.

Figure 9: Penetration depth versus time for carbon fiber/N6 towpreg. The resin content is 43weight%. The processing pressure is 0.52 MPa and the processing temperature is 260 °C. The standard deviation of the penetration depth is ~0.002 mm.

For the towpreg experiments, the error for the semi-empirical model varied between 3 and 9 % . The average error was 5.5%. For the same experiments the average error for the Brusckke model was 5.8 %, virtually the same. It should be noted that the Brusckke model can be related to the Kozeny-Carman equation to determine a Kozeny constant. When doing this and using the fiber volume fraction of 0.76 calculated for the towpreg, a Kozeny constant of 368 was calculated. This number compares well with the Kozeny constant values calculated with the semi-empirical model.

Figure 10 presents a more extensive prediction of the Kozeny constant using the Brusckhe model. It is apparent that the Kozeny constant is quite sensitive to the porosity and power-law flow index, particularly at low porosities. Also, it is apparent that permeation is facilitated when a highly shear-thinning (low flow index) fluid is used.

Figure 10: Graph of Kozeny constant calculated from Brusckhe model versus porosity with power-law flow index as a parameter

CONCLUSIONS

The permeation of thermoplastics during the processing of composites from random fiber mat preforms and unidirectional powder-coated towpreg was studied. A transverse Kozeny constant of 7.9 was determined for the mat preform processing, and it was found that a semi-empirical model with this Kozeny constant predicts penetration depth well in the mat. A transverse Kozeny constant of 362 was calculated for the towpreg processing. The semi-empirical model also predicted the permeation depth well for the towpreg processing.

A model for flow transverse to a square array of cylinders, developed by Brusckhe and Advani (4), predicted the transient permeation in both mats and towpregs well. Since this model worked well without requiring any adjustable parameters, it is preferred. The model due to Vijaysri *et al* (2) worked well for mats, but not as well as the model due to Brushke and Advani (4).

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